

LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK APHORISMS

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Annotation: A language mirrors the specific culture of its nation, especially, aphorisms' role in reflecting national features and culture of this nation is extensive. Traditions of people and culture peculiarities are expressed in aphorisms.

Key words: linguoculturology, cultureme, interrelation, aphorismos, aristocratic.

Aphorism was originally used in the world of medicine. Credit Hippocrates, the Greek physician regarded as the father of modern medicine, with influencing our use of the word. He used aphorismos in titling a book outlining his principles on the diagnosis and treatment of disease. That volume offered many examples that helped to define aphorism, beginning with the statement that starts the book's introduction: "Life is short, Art long, Occasion sudden and dangerous, Experience deceitful, and Judgment difficult". English speakers originally used the term mainly in the realm of the physical sciences, but eventually broadened its use to cover principles in other fields. Aphoristic collections, sometimes known as wisdom literature, have a prominent place in the canons of several ancient societies, such as the Sutra literature of India, the Islamic hadiths, the golden verses of Pythagoras, Hesiod's Works and Days, the Delphic maxims, and Epictetus' Handbook. A famous writer S. Sontag gives a definition to an aphorism in her book: "An aphorism is aristocratic thinking". It is clear from the definition that aphorisms are usually based on a general truth and have figurative meaning. An aphorism is a product of the definite nation as a folk saying during considerable long time. They are handed down through years and ages as frames or models of human life typical situations. Some scholars (Seiler, Firth, etc.) mentioned in their works that the main reason of aphorisms in folklore is their traditionality.

Actually, aphorisms picture studying practically a great deal of details of the everyday life of even ordinary people. Many linguists have offered a method of discussing aphorisms as cultural texts based on the linguocultural level of language and the cultureme as its basic structural unit. The term "linguoculturology" has been supposed to be used as a separate linguistic field since the beginning of the previous XX century. This field studies interrelation of language and culture, mutual

influence on the development of culture and language, their links with social life, psychology, and philosophy. Because a language cannot exist without a culture of a nation and a culture also cannot survive without a language as well. Linguoculturology is one of the main aspects of linguistic investigations, it deals with various issues that relate with language spirit and cultural variation of a nation, encompasses various national-cultural notions and theories of conversational structure. This branch studies national spirit that is reflected in a language. It is associated with other studies as philosophy, logics, sociology, anthropology and semantics; and covers national and cultural knowledge through speech communication. In the book of linguist U.K. Yusupov “Contrastive linguistics of the English and Uzbek languages” it is clearly mentioned that linguocultureme is a linguistic or speech unit. The term “linguoculturology” has been supposed to be used as a separate linguistic field since the beginning of the previous XX century. This field studies interrelation of language and culture, mutual influence on the development of culture and language, their links with social life, psychology, and philosophy. Because a language cannot exist without a culture of a nation and a culture also cannot survive without a language as well.

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It is obvious that appearing and forming of aphorisms takes considerably long period of time. The history of English language is believed to be long. English has background that comes from the Latin language. Nevertheless, there are four main sources of English language, which are European source, including English, namely the Greek and the Roman Antiquity, the Bible, the Medieval Latin and the loan translation. This article aims to analyse linguo-cultural features of proverbs in English languages with the help of famous aphorisms and their analogue in Uzbek.

1) A man is known by a company he keeps – Do‘sting kimligini ayt seni kimligingni aytaman. (Tell me your friend and I will tell you who you are) In these aphorism it is said that man’s qualities are determined by what kind of friends he has. In semantic point of view, these two expressions seem identical, but their pragmatic features are different: the English proverb is usually used in more formal and literary styles, in its turn the Uzbek one is mostly applied in colloquial speech. 2) A friend in court is better than a penny in purse.– 10 so‘m puling bo‘lmasin, 10 ta do‘sting bo‘lsin. (Money is not wealth, friendship is wealth) This aphorism contains a word “penny” which comes from English culture. 3) Procrastination is a thief of time.- Bugungi

ishni ertaga qoldirma. (Never do tomorrow what you can do today) The origin of the word “procrastination” is Latin language. As it was mentioned before Latin is one of the sources of English language.

To conclude, aphorisms are essential part of the English and any other language. They have differences in semantics, structure, stylistics and even pragmatic meaning. Aphorisms contain many aspects of the culture of a nation. Aphorisms serve to describe, define and express the culture of the language in which they exist. It is important to emphasize that aphorisms contain social practices that can be visualized in a real or possible world. In addition, there is unstoppable process of language changes, due to that, the quantity of aphorisms in the language also changes; some of them may disappear, people may start using some other new aphorisms in their daily speech.

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